

Public Distribution System as a strategy to achieve Sustainable Development Goals-2030 and Food Security: A case analysis of Kalahandi District, Odisha

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Abstract: This article evaluates the impact of the Public Distribution System (PDS) on rural poverty to accomplish the food security goal by using the Global Hunger Index (GHI), the National Sample Survey (NSS), and data collected from Odisha Economic Survey and the Odisha State Civil Supplies Corporation Ltd (OSCSC). In today's scenario, India's Global Hunger Index is very high, at 27.5, indicating that people in India are still hungry. In rural India, the Public Distribution System (PDS) is a kind of economic support and social protection scheme that aims to give two square meals to every impoverished household to reduce the country's hunger index. The National Sample Survey indicates that around 6% of the overall population of the country sleeps without two square meals every day and this section is called 'Hungry'. This article focuses on the Public Distribution System (PDS) and its importance in the food security of Odisha's underdeveloped and poor people of Kalahandi. Poverty is at its worst and most frightening in Odisha Kalahandi. This article examines and evaluates the Kalahandi district's Public Distribution System, highlighting its success and the rural poor's food security status. The outcome of food security must be taken into account in this context because Kalahandi is one of Odisha's food insecure districts, and the government's goal is to abolish poverty and hunger for all people worldwide. As a result, the Indian government is investing in rural welfare initiatives, which are contributing significantly to the reduction of national and state poverty levels by 2030.

Keywords: - Food Security, Public Distribution System (PDS), Sustainable Development Goals, Poverty, Global Hunger

“Recall the face of the poorest and the weakest man [woman] whom you may have seen, and ask yourself if the step you contemplate is going to be of any use to him [her].”

Gandhiji’s Talisman

Introduction

From the prehistoric period to the digital realm food is the basic need of every human being, without which a man cannot survive. According to Abraham Maslow among Food, Cloth, and Shelter, Food comes first in the Hierarchy of Needs Theory (*Abraham Maslow, the concept of a hierarchy of needs - 1943 "A Theory of Human Motivation"*), followed by clothes and shelter.¹ It lays the foundation for the fulfillment of all other requirements. In 1997, the government implemented the Targeted Public Distribution System (TPDS). The major goal of implementing this plan was to provide subsidies at their doorstep to those who earn less than the poverty level. States were obligated to undertake surveys to identify families living Below the Poverty Line (BPL) income criterion set by the Planning Commission. Mahatma Gandhi remarked in 'Young India' in 1920, that "We need to organize our nutritional power not by adopting the best technique of production only, but by the best way of both production and distribution," The Public Distribution System (PDS) is in desperate need of change. It needs to be strengthened and strengthening the Public Distribution System would ensure that people have access to the fundamental necessities of life.

Given the importance of food for human development and survival, which indirectly converts to a strong and successful world, since the 1940s internationally ensuring sufficient and excellent quality of food for each human being has been recognized. According to Article 25(1) of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights Food security is a core human right. Since then, many scholars and policymakers have defined food security in several ways.

Odisha has a population of 41,947,218 people, with 40% of the population living below the poverty and 87% of the population living in rural regions, with 70% of people who depend on agriculture as their major source of income.² The state government, in partnership with the central government, is implementing the Public Distribution System (PDS) intending to protect low-income populations by supplying the minimum necessary food grains at reasonable costs.

¹ Maslow, Abraham H.(2011) “A Theory of Human Motivation” Psychology Classics, p.14

² Odisha Economic Survey 2020-21, Planning And Convergence Department, Government of Odisha p.32

There are about 8582108 BPL (Below Poverty Line), APL (Above Poverty Line), AAY (Antyodaya Anna Yojana), and ANP (Annapurna) cardholders in the State. The primary objective of implementing the Public Distribution System in Odisha is to reduce future poverty and hunger percentages and to strengthen the Socioeconomic condition of poor people.

Even though many efforts have been taken to assure food security for every human being, poverty, hunger, and malnutrition are all too widespread in developing and undeveloped countries around the world. Food output has increased dramatically during the last half-century. Despite this, more than one in seven individuals today do not get enough protein and energy from their diet, and countless more suffer from micronutrient malnutrition.

The declaration of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and the Global Hunger Index (GHI) statistic.

The 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, which were endorsed by world leaders during a historic UN Summit in September 2015, went into effect on January 1, 2016. Over the next fifteen years, governments will organize efforts to eradicate all forms of poverty, combat inequality, and combat climate change, while guaranteeing that no one is left behind. Sustainable Development Goal 2 (SDG 2 or Global Goal 2) aims to achieve "Zero Hunger" and it is one of the United Nations' 17 Sustainable Development Goals. According to the official language "End hunger, establish Food Security and Enhanced Nutrition, and promote Sustainable Agriculture," However, six years after the SDGs were declared, the proclamation and reality are vastly different. Because, according to the most current Global Hunger Index (GHI), India is Under the serious category that is 27.5.³

According to the latest estimates (Tendulkar Committee estimates) during 2004-05 and 2011-12, the rural poverty in Odisha had been reduced by 25.1 percentage points that is from 60.8% to 35.69% whereas the reduction was 16.1% at the national level from 41.8% to 25.7% under Head Count Ratio (HCR). However, the Poverty Gap Ratio (PGR) was reduced by about 10.36% for rural Odisha against the rate of reduction for rural India of 4.59%. Although poverty incidence, as well as poverty gap, was higher for rural Odisha than that of rural India, the

³ Columbia Center on Sustainable Investment (CCSI), et al. "SDG2: Zero Hunger." *Mapping Mining to the Sustainable Development Goals: An Atlas*, Sustainable Development Solutions Network, 2016, pp. 20–22. JSTOR, <http://www.jstor.org/stable/resrep15880.7>. Accessed 8 Jun. 2022.

reduction rate was significantly higher in rural Odisha than that of the national figure.⁴ As we were aware the Global Hunger Index (GHI) is a method for measuring and tracking hunger on a global, regional, and country level it is calculated once a year and the findings are published in an annual report in October. The recent GHI report of 2021 shows a serious hunger situation resulting from a terrible mix of the climate crisis, the COVID-19 pandemic, and increasingly severe and protracted conflicts. Progress toward the Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) of "Zero Hunger by 2030," which had already been much too slow, has stalled or even reversed in certain nations.

The report for 2021 focuses on the interconnections between conflicts and hunger and presents recommendations regarding how to break these links so that peace and food security can be achieved. The Hunger Index assesses a country's performance on four key indicators: malnutrition, child wasting, stunting, and mortality. The current Hunger Index for 2021 is the 16th publication (since 2006) and India is ranked 101 out of 116 countries in the Global Hunger Index 2021 (down from 94 in the previous year).

Source: <https://www.globalhungerindex.org/>

The above Global Hunger Index shows India's Performance on GHI's Indicators:

⁴ Odisha Economic Survey 2020-21, Planning And Convergence Department, Government of Odisha p.116

- Undernourishment - 35 percent of India's total population is undernourished.
- Child Wasting – 19.3 percent of children are reported to be wasted.
- Child Stunting – 34.7 percent of children are reported to be stunted.
- Child mortality – 3.7 percent of children died before the age of five.

India has dropped seven places since 2020 when it was ranked 94th. India is ranked lower than the majority of its neighbors. Pakistan, for example, has a score of 92, Sri Lanka has a score of 65, Nepal has a score of 76, and Bangladesh has a score of 76. According to the most recent data, Only 15 countries are ranked lower than India in the 2021 index. India has the greatest rate of child wasting of all the countries in the ranking. Other metrics, such as the under-5 mortality rate, the frequency of stunting in children, and the prevalence of undernourishment due to insufficient food, still exist in India.

The aforementioned facts indicate that people in India are still hungry today and that substantial attention is needed at both the national and regional levels to combat hunger in India.

Public Distribution System (PDS) in India to achieve Food Security and combat Hunger

The public Distribution System (PDS) is one of the government's largest welfare programs, assisting farmers in selling their goods at fair prices and assisting the underprivileged segments of society in purchasing food grains at reasonable prices.

PDS was implemented as a rationing measure during World War II. Before the 1960s, food grain imports were the primary source of distribution through PDS. It was extended in the 1960s in response to food shortages, and the government later established the Agriculture Pricing Commission as well as the FCI to increase domestic purchase and preservation of grain crops for the PDS. PDS had transformed into a countrywide program for the delivery of subsidized food by the 1970s. It was indeed a general entitlement mechanism for all consumers before 1992, with no defined aim. The Revamped Public Distribution System (RPDS) was launched in June 1992 intending to strengthen and streamline the PDS, it also expand its coverage into even more, hilly, isolated, and inaccessible places where a significant portion of the disadvantaged community lives. The Targeted Public Distribution System (TPDS) was started by the Indian government in June 1997 and targets the disadvantaged section. Beneficiaries of the TPDS were categorized into two categories, those living below the poverty

line (BPL) and those living above the poverty line (APL). Antyodaya Anna Yojana (AAY) was also a step toward ensuring that TPDS aimed to alleviate hunger among the poorest parts of the BPL population. According to the National Sample Survey (NSS) data, around 5% of the overall population in this country sleep without having two square meals per day. to make the TPDS more focused and targeted towards this group of people. The "Antyodaya Anna Yojana" (AAY) was started in December 2000 for a crore of the poorest of the poor families in India. ⁵

Finally, the Parliament of India passed the National Food Security Act 2013 (commonly known as the "Right to Food Act"), which intends to give subsidized food grains to around two-thirds of the country's 1.2 billion inhabitants. On September 12, 2013, it was signed into law and the National Food Security Act of 2013 (NFSA 2013) converts the existing government of India's food security programs into legal entitlements. The Midday Meal Scheme, Integrated Child Development Services, and the Public Distribution System are all part of it. In addition, the NFSA 2013 also acknowledges maternity benefits. The Midday Meal Scheme and the Integrated Child Development Services Scheme are both universal, whereas the PDS will be available to around two-thirds of the population (75 percent in rural areas and 50 percent in urban areas).

Government Schemes		
Scheme	Year Introduced	Coverage Target Group
Public Distribution System (PDS)	Up to 1992	Universal
Revamped Public Distribution System (RPDS)	1992	Backward Blocks
Targeted Public Distribution System (TPDS)	1997	Poor and non-poor (APL, BPL)
Antyodaya Anna Yojana (AAY)	2000	Poorest of the Poor
Annapurna Scheme	2000	Indigent Senior Citizens
National Food Security Act, 2013 (NFSA)	2013	Priority household

⁵ Pathania, Kulwant Singh, "Public Distribution System - Status, Challenges, and Remedial Strategies, Kaniska Publication.

Even though nearly 12 crore BPL cards have been distributed, and still poverty and hunger remain a challenge. The overwhelming majority of needy impoverished people remain unprotected by social welfare. In Odisha, ensuring food and nutrition security for all people remains a pipe dream. The position of PDS is now being examined in this regard. According to the BPL Census 2011, a total of 13,670,644 lakhs people in Odisha live below the poverty line, representing 32.59 percent of the state's total population. This paints a bleak picture of Odisha's food security.⁶

The above diagram shows how Public Distribution System Works in India,

Public Distribution System (PDS) in Kalahandi, Odisha: Paving the way to food security:

“It is my endeavor that not a single poor man is deprived of food security.”

-Naveen Patnaik (Hon’ble Chief Minister Odisha)

Everyone requires food to live a dignified life. Providing adequate food to a national population emphasizes the significance of a systematic approach to effectively address this

⁶ Odisha State Civil Supplies Corporation Limited, Food Supplies & Consumer Welfare Department, Govt. of Odisha

challenge. The government of Odisha, in collaboration with stakeholders such as the corporate sector, non-profit organizations, administrative bodies, and civil society, was able to transform the scenario of the state's food security. The Hon'ble Chief Minister of Odisha Naveen Patnaik and the government of Odisha are attempting to build Odisha as a model state for food security in India, based on the 5Ts (Transparency, Technology, Teamwork, Time-Bound, and Transformation).

The population of Odisha according to 2011 census is about 4,19,74,218 out of which 2,12,12,136 are males and 2,07,62,082 are females. The State accounts for approximately 3.4 percent of the country's population, up from around 3 percent in the last census in 2011. The population density per sq. km is 269, which is lower than the national average. The state's literacy rate is around 73.45 percent, a figure that has risen dramatically in recent years as a result of the government's constant efforts. Odisha's sex ratio is 978, and it has never been a state with a significant drop in this percentage. Around 87 percent of the population lives in rural areas, with 70 percent of people relying on agriculture as their primary source of income. Kalahandi is a district in Odisha, India and according to the 2011 Indian census, Kalahandi has a population of 15,76,869, with 7,87,101 males and 7,89,768 females. A total of 1,21,987 people live in urban regions, while 14,54,882 live in rural areas.⁷

The State Government is implementing the Public Distribution System (PDS) in collaboration with the Central Government to protect poor groups by supplying the minimum required quantities of food grains at reasonable prices and controlling open market rises in commodities prices by ensuring equitable distribution to the community. Under the PDS, the government, in collaboration with numerous parties, provides rice as the major commodity, as well as maize, sugar, and kerosene. There are approximately 8582108 BPL (Below Poverty Line), APL (Above Poverty Line), AAY (Antyodaya Anna Yojana), and ANP (Annapurna) cardholders in the State. Throughout the state, different cardholders are chosen based on their eligibility criteria. Under the Companies Act, 1956, the Odisha State Civil Supplies Corporation Ltd (OSCSC) was established on September 3, 1980, as a completely owned State Government Corporation, the Odisha Government and OSCS Ltd are working together with the Central Government to ensure food security for the needy poor of Odisha. With the

⁷ Office of the Registrar General & Census Commissioner, India Ministry of Home Affairs, Government of India

cooperation of stakeholders in the State, OSCSC Ltd is taking the responsibility for the procurement, purchase, warehousing, and distribution of PDS goods.

In less than two decades, the state went from a paddy output deficit to a paddy production surplus. Currently, the state is ranked 4th in the country, contributing 9.36% of the country's total paddy procurement. In comparison to the previous years, the state procured 70.57 MT of paddy in the Kharif Marketing Session (KMS) 2019-20. The graphical representation below represents the amount of paddy procured over the years in Lakh Metric Tonnes (LMT).

Source: Dept. of Food Supplies & Consumer Welfare, Govt. of Odisha

The above data indicate that Odisha's government distributes subsidized food grains to over 3.34 million individuals, feeding roughly 3/4 population of the state. After meeting its requirements, the government gives the surplus amount of rice to the Food Corporation of India, which distributes it to other states. In Kharif Marketing Season (KMS) 2019-20, 70.57 lakh MT of paddy has been procured by the state from 11.61 lakh farmers living in 50,000+ villages of the state.⁸

The Government's Poverty Alleviation scheme to achieve food security in Kalahandi

To alleviate poverty in Kalahandi, the government of Odisha provides various food grains at a cheap price through the Public Distribution Scheme, however, the truth is that the poor do not even have the minimum cash to purchase PDS commodities. Due to a lack of communication, road, and infrastructure, tribal people in hilly locations walk 17 kilometers to

⁸ Government of Odisha Food Supplies & consumer welfare department, Making of a Food Secure Odisha. 2021, p. 31

obtain PDS supplies. Hence different Schemes have been taken up by Government to eradicate Poverty and strengthen the economic condition of the people to achieve food security in the Kalahandi District. The PDS is a special scheme in Kalahandi under the food safety net, however other rural development schemes are also introduced to achieve economic and social security in Kalahandi like SGRY (Swaranajayanti Gram Swarozagar Yozana), NREGS (National Rural Employment Gramin Scheme), MDM (Mid-day meals), AAY (Antyodaya yojana), NOAPS (National Old Age Pension Annapurna Scheme) which has 100 percent of NOAPS card holder in Kalahandi, they are receiving regular and full old age pensions, but ICDS (Integrated Child Development Services), which is 20% in Kalahandi district, has not received any benefit, and NMBS, (National Maternity Benefit Scheme). In Kalahandi, NMBS has the worst performance of all the food security and poverty reduction schemes.

Concluding Remarks

Odisha was troubled by a faulty public distribution system nearly two decades ago. The technique of identifying recipients had several flaws. Leakages were common due to a lack of transparency in on-the-ground operations and stakeholder accountability, impeding the distribution of food grains to those who earned them. Odisha went back to the drawing board to fully rebuild the public distribution system, recognizing its important role in giving direct help to the needy. My findings in this article contain both positive and negative findings. The good news is that India's public distribution system is now clearly having an impact on rural poverty. The impact is especially significant in states with a well-functioning PDS, confirming recent evidence that the PDS is now a major source of economic security for the poor. The bad news is that the PDS has minimal impact on rural poverty in several areas where infrastructure, communication, and road facilities are lacking, as in Odisha's Kalahandi district, where PDS changes have been long delayed. I hope that further NSS will reveal indications of the PDS's sustained resurrection across the country and state.

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